

Supplementary Information for Emergence of Kinship Structures and Descent Systems: Multi-level Evolutionary Simulation and Empirical Data Analyses

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SUPPLEMENTARY TEXT

Detailed Estimation of the Phase Diagrams of Kinship Structures

To estimate the environmental dependence of the evolved structures in Figs. 3 and 5, we calculated the fitness of each structure. We assume that the traits and preferences in the clans follow a multivariate normal distribution. We also assume that the variables t_1, t_2, p_1 , and p_2 are independent and have the same variance σ^2 . Thus, the probability function of the traits and preferences of the families in the incest structure, with its cluster centre at $(\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{p}) = ((t_1^*, t_2^*), (p_1^*, p_2^*))$, is given by

$$f(t_1, t_2, p_1, p_2) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \right)^4 \exp \left(- \frac{(t_1 - t_1^*)^2 + (t_2 - t_2^*)^2 + (p_1 - p_1^*)^2 + (p_2 - p_2^*)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right). \quad (\text{S1})$$

The average values of *friend* in the same clan (kin) and, similarly, those of *rival* would be

$$\langle \text{friend} \rangle = \int \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \right)^4 \exp(-|t^a - t^b|^2 / \tau^2) \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$\exp \left(- \frac{(t_1^a - t_1^*)^2 + (t_2^a - t_2^*)^2 + (t_1^b - t_1^*)^2 + (t_2^b - t_2^*)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) dt_1^a dt_2^a dt_1^b dt_2^b \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\sigma^2 / \tau^2 + 1} = \langle \text{rival} \rangle. \quad (\text{S4})$$

Next, we recall that clusters emerge and are sustained depending on the fluctuation of traits and preferences. The centres of the groom and bride clans deviate with the order of the mutation rate μ . Thus, for example, the centres of clans in dual organisations would be $(\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{p}) = ((a, b), (c, d))$ and $((b + \delta\mu, a + \delta\mu), (d + \delta\mu, c + \delta\mu))$ (, where $\delta \sim O(1)$). The average values of *friend* in the mate's clan would be

$$\langle \text{friend} \rangle = \int \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \right)^4 \exp(-|t^a - \mathbf{p}^b|^2 / \tau^2) \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$\exp \left(- \frac{(t_1^a - t_1^*)^2 + (t_2^a - t_2^*)^2 + (p_1^b - t_1^* - \delta\mu)^2 + (p_2^b - t_2^* - \delta\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) dt_1^a dt_2^a dp_1^b dp_2^b \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\sigma^2 / \tau^2 + 1} \exp \left(- \frac{\delta^2 \mu^2}{4\sigma^2 + \tau^2} \right). \quad (\text{S7})$$

Hence, considering the variance in the (\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{p}) distribution leads to multiplying $\frac{1}{4\sigma^2 / \tau^2 + 1}$ by each value of $\langle \text{friend} \rangle$ and $\langle \text{rival} \rangle$ in Table 2; the α values therein are given by $\frac{\delta^2}{4\sigma^2 + \tau^2}$. Because these multiplication factors are common to every value, the conditions of the phase boundaries are qualitatively consistent with those in the main text.

Furthermore, we estimated the probability of sustaining each structure. In each simulation step, the population of each clan fluctuates owing to the number of births, which follow a Poisson distribution. In

addition, there is a random walk in the (t, p) space. Hence, if all families in the clan have no children, or all their children leave the cluster, the clan will disappear. This can occur if the population is finite. We set the probability of a family not having children in their cluster to q . When there are N families, composing the n clans in the society, the probability of sustaining the structure is $p = 1 - nq^{N/n}$. This increases as the number of clans increases. As n is 1, 2, 3, and 4 for the incest structure, dual organisation, generalised exchange, and restricted exchange, respectively, the above sustenance probabilities (p_I for the incest structure, p_D for dual organisation, p_G for generalised exchange, and p_R for restricted exchange) decline in this order. In addition, as μ increases, p decreases; as N_f increases, p decreases; and as N_s increases, the probability of sampling corrupted societies decreases. Hence, p_I, p_D, p_G , and p_R will increase to 1 when N_f or N_s is large or μ is small.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. Geographic distribution of kinship structures. Incest, dual organisation, generalised exchange, and restricted exchange are plotted in yellow, green, orange, and pink, respectively. This information is based on [1, 2]. Owing to data shortages, kinship structures were identified in 60 of the 186 societies in the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample (SCCS). There were 22 societies identified as incest structures, 14 as dual organisation structures, 15 as generalised exchange structures, and 9 as restricted exchange structures. We only used the data of 24 societies in which sufficient data were available to estimate \bar{d}_c and \bar{d}_m in Fig. 4(B).

Figure S2. Geographic distribution of descent systems. Patrilineal, matrilineal, and double descent systems are plotted in orange, blue, and yellow, respectively. Information is based on [1, 2]. Descent systems were identified in all 186 societies in the SCCS. There were 75 societies identified as patrilineal, 26 as matrilineal, and 10 as double descent systems. Furthermore, descent lines were traced either paternally or maternally in each generation (so-called ambilineal descent) in six societies, and kin groups were not observed in 69 societies, which are omitted from the figure. We only used the data of 34 societies in which sufficient data were available to identify kinship structures, as shown in Fig. 5(B).

Figure S3. Phase diagram of the kinship structures against the parameters d_c and d_m . By analysing the SCCS, we estimated d_c and d_m for each society and plotted the dependencies of their kinship structures. The incest structure is plotted in yellow, dual organisation in green, generalised exchange in orange, and restricted exchange in pink. Incest structures are spread widely in the diagram. This may be because societies with such structures can have social systems other than kinship influencing their adoption of these conditions.

Figure S4. Dependency of descent systems on kinship structures. Figures show the frequency of each descent system, both theoretically and empirically. The frequencies of matrilineal (yellow), patrilineal (orange), and double descent (green) systems are shown. (A) Theoretical phase diagram. The model was simulated by changing the d_c and d_m values. We calculated the frequencies of each descent system for each kinship structure. In Fig. 5(A), $N_f = 50$. Here, $N_f = 30$. (B) Empirical phase diagram. By analysing the SCCS, we identified descent systems and kinship structures for each society. We counted the frequencies of each descent system for each kinship structure.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Table S1. Identification of kinship structures. Structures are categorised by referring to the descent system, exogamous units, and cousin preferences for mates. Exclusive conditions for identifying the same class are described in different rows.

Structure	Explanation	Criterion
Incest structure	No exogamy	"219" < 3 and "222" = "224" = 1
Dual organisation	Patrilineal moiety exogamy	"222" = 6 and "224" = 1
	Matrilineal moiety exogamy	"222" = 1 and "224" = 6
	Patrilineal descent with symmetrical cross-cousin preference	"70" = 3 and "224" = "230" = 1
	Matrilineal descent with symmetrical cross-cousin preference	"70" = 1 and "222" = "230" = 1
Generalised exchange	Patrilineal descent with MoBrDa preference	"70" = 3 and "230" = 3
	Patrilineal exogamy with MoBrDa preference	"222" > 1 and "230" = 3
	Matrilineal descent with FaSiDa preference	"70" = 3 and "230" = 2
	Matrilineal exogamy with FaSiDa preference	"224" > 1 and "230" = 2
Restricted exchange	Exogamy concerning both patrilineal and matrilineal kins	"222" > 1 and "224" > 1
	Double descent with symmetrical cross-cousin preference	"70" = 2 and "230" = 1

Table S2. Correlation between variables in the SCCS and kinship structures. For pairs of kinship structures (dual organisation, generalised exchange, and restricted exchange), Spearman's rank correlations between the SCCS variables and the structures were calculated. Then, the absolute values of the correlations were averaged for each pair. This table shows the variables that exhibited high correlation, together with the average of the absolute values of its correlation, and the average value of the variables for each structure. The last two columns show the fraction of available data for each variable and the corresponding parameters in the model. The top 12 variables in the correlation are shown above the dashed line; the five variables under the dashed line are included because they could also be relevant to the model parameters. Generally, a larger value for each item shows that the item is observed to a greater degree in societies (e.g. a large value for SCCS1772 shows that hostility toward other ethnic groups is strong). Most variables with high correlation are related to d_c , d_m , gender balance, or the other parameters of our model. SCCS973, SCCS983, and SCCS1767 suggest that gender inequality is most frequently observed in generalised exchange, followed (in order) by dual organisation and restricted exchange. As discussed in the main text, patrilineal descent is more dominant in generalised exchange and less dominant in dual organisation, whereas double descent is adopted in restricted exchange. Because paternal kin are highly recognised in patrilineal descent and both paternal and maternal kin are recognised equally in double descent, the above trend of gender inequality is reasonable. As for the other parameters, SCCS1756 influences N_f , and SCCS1865 influences N_s . The trend of SCCS1865 shows that a large (or small) N_s leads to the evolution of restricted (or generalised) exchange across larger parameter regions, which is consistent with Fig. 7.

Name	Explanation	Corr.	Dual	Generalised	Restricted	Ratio	Model
SCCS1689	Sex Ratio (Males/Females*10)	0.71	10.5	8.02	11.4	0.29	—
SCCS1772	Hostility towards Other Ethnic Groups	0.68	37.4	29.4	10	0.39	d_c
SCCS939	Personal Restrictions on Regular Menstruation	0.65	4.75	5	1.5	0.21	—
SCCS973	Degree of Marriage Celebration	0.64	3	2.67	4	0.26	—
SCCS1737	Extent of Burden Caused by Tribute Payments or Taxation	0.63	32	27	23.7	0.29	d_c
SCCS173	Rape	0.63	1	3.5	3.5	0.16	d_m
SCCS983	Property Exchanges after Divorce	0.62	4	5	3.5	0.16	—
SCCS782	(Un) Acceptability of Violence within the Society	0.61	4	2.33	2.33	0.37	d_m
SCCS58	General Indulgence, Infancy	0.59	2.75	1.83	1.33	0.53	—
SCCS768	(No) Conflict between Communities of the Same Society	0.59	3.29	2.12	1.33	0.47	d_m
SCCS1770	Attitude towards Violence against Other Ethnic Groups	0.56	30.8	24	30	0.21	d_c
SCCS960	Violation of the Incest Taboo	0.54	2.33	4	6	0.13	d_m
SCCS791	Cross-cutting Ties across Communities	0.51	2.14	1	1.33	0.47	d_c
SCCS962	Violation of Restrictions on Premarital Sex	0.46	2	2.5	5	0.29	d_m
SCCS905	Rewards	0.40	1.67	1.33	2.4	0.61	d_c
SCCS1756	Size of Local Community	0.39	186.67	88.71	120	0.39	N_f
SCCS1767	Ideology of Male Superiority	0.28	1.57	1.17	2.0	0.45	—
SCCS1865	Number of Societies within 150 Mile Radius	0.28	1.86	1.53	3.89	1	N_s

Values of SCCS Variables Used for Data Analyses

The values of SCCS variables are explained as below, according to [1–14]

SCCS70 Descent - Membership in Corporate Kinship Groups

1 Matrilineal—through female line, 2 Double descent—separate groups through male and female lines, 3 Patrilineal—through male line, 4 Ambilineal—through one parent in each generation, and 5 Bilateral—not a corporate kin group

SCCS219 Community marriage organisation [Note, identical to EA015]

1 Demes, 2 Segmented (no exogamy), 3 Agamous, 4 Exogamous, 5 Segmented (exogamy), and 6 Clans

SCCS222 Largest patrilineal exogamous group [Note, identical to EA018]

1 No exogamy, 2 Extended taboo, 3 Lineages, 4 Sibs, 5 Phratries, and 6 Moieties

SCCS224 Largest matrilineal exogamous group [Note, identical to EA020]

1 No exogamy, 2 Extended taboo, 3 Lineages, 4 Sibs, 5 Phratries, and 6 Moieties

SCCS230 Cousin marriages preferred: subtypes [Note, identical to EA026]

1 Symmetrical cross-cousin, 2 MoBrDa, 3 FaSiDa, 4 FaBrDa, 5 Second cousin, and 9 None preferred

SCCS1689 Sex Ratio (Males/Females*10)

Number of males / number of females × 10

SCCS1772 Hostility towards Other Ethnic Groups

10 no or negligible hostility, 20 weak degree of hostility, 30 moderate degree of hostility, 31 moderate degree of hostility only directed against certain other ethnic groups, 32 moderate degree of hostility directed against almost all other ethnic groups, 40 high degree of hostility, 41 high degree of hostility only directed against certain other ethnic groups, and 42 high degree of hostility directed against almost all other ethnic groups

SCCS939 Personal Restrictions or Regular Menstruation

1 No restriction during this period, 2 Restrictions on personal activities but not social activities, 3 Restrictions on personal and social movements, 4 Few restrictions placed on personal and social activities, 5 Moderate restrictions (may not cook), and 6 Severe restrictions secluded in a menstrual hut

SCCS1737 Extent of Burden Caused by Tribute Payments or Taxation

20 sporadic taxation or request for tribute, 21 sporadic exactions are reported not to be burdensome, 22 sporadic exactions are reported to be burdensome, 30 regular taxation or request for tribute, 31 regular exactions are reported not to be burdensome, and 32 regular exactions are reported to be burdensome

SCCS173 Rape

1 Accepted/ignored, 2 Ridiculed, 3 Mildly disapproved, and 4 Strongly disapproved

SCCS983 Property Exchanges after Divorce. Ranked in order of the amount of financial loss incurred by the wife when a divorce occurs

1 There is no divorce, 2 No financial transaction occurs after a divorce (equal share), 3 The husband or his kin pay compensation, 4 The transaction that occurs depends on the circumstances, and 6 The wife and/or her kin group pay compensation

SCCS782 (Un) Acceptability of Violence toward Members of the Same Society, but outside the Local Community

1 Valued, 2 Acceptable, 3 Tolerated, and 4 Disapproved

SCCS58 General Indulgence, Infancy—Modifiers of General Scale Types

1 Low, 2 Medium, and 3 High

SCCS768 (No) Conflict between Communities of the Same Society

1 Endemic, 2 High, 3 Moderate, and 4 Mild or rare

SCCS1770 Attitude towards Physical Violence against Members of Other Ethnic Groups

10 Physical violence outside of ethnic group is rejected, 11 Physical violence outside of ethnic group is rejected because of military inferiority or cowardice, 20 Physical violence is tolerated or accepted—specification of the enemies is absent, 21 Physical violence is tolerated or accepted but not against the majority of other ethnic groups, 22 Physical violence is tolerated or accepted against the majority of other ethnic groups, 30 Physical violence is appreciated—no further specification against whom, 31 Physical violence is appreciated but not against the majority of other ethnic groups, and 32 physical violence is appreciated against the majority of other ethnic groups

SCCS960 Violation of the Incest Taboo

1 None or mild punishment, 2 Moderate punishment, 3 Severe punishment, 4 Punishment to those other than the offenders, 5 Punishment to the whole social group, and 6 Punishment that affects the offenders and their social group

SCCS791 Type of Cross-cutting Ties: Moieties Cutting across Communities

1 Absent, 2 Present but unimportant, and 3 Present and important

SCCS962 Violation of Restrictions on Premarital Sex. Each category specifies the consequences a woman faces if she violates premarital sex prohibition

1 Neither she nor her partner face punishment, 2 Her partner is punished, but she is not, 3 Mild punishment for the women, 4 Moderate punishment for the woman, 5 Severe punishment, banished from social group or killed, and 6 Severe or killed ?

SCCS905 Rewards (Special Gifts, Praises, or Ceremonies, Not including Ritual Purification) for a Man Who Has Killed an Enemy in Battle or Otherwise Shown Skill in War

1 Usually or Always, 2 Sometimes, and 3 Rarely or never

SCCS1756 Size of Local Community

Population of local community

SCCS1767 Ideology of Male Superiority

1 no ideology of male superiority, 2 weakly articulated ideology of male superiority, and 3 strongly articulated ideology of male superiority (it is the basic determinant of gender relations)

SCCS1865 Concordance: Number of Societies within 150 Mile Radius

The number of societies within a 150-mile radius

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